

Association of Serum Magnesium Level with Retinopathy in Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus

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ABSTRACT

Magnesium is an intracellular cation and coenzyme for various reactions of the glycolytic pathway. Hypomagnesemia has been shown to precipitate hyperglycemia and has, therefore, been implicated in insulin resistance and its microvascular complications. Poor glycemic control has been associated with retinopathy. Hence, we assessed association of serum magnesium with T2DM and diabetic retinopathy among 100 patients with type 2 Diabetic Mellitus (with complications) with their ophthalmological complications (retinopathy) admitted in People's College of Medical Sciences & Research Centre, Bhopal. Estimation of serum magnesium was done by spectrophotometric method using xylydyl blue. Comparison of serum magnesium level in patients with and without retinopathy in uncontrolled Diabetic patients. Serum magnesium level was 2.03 ± 0.33 among no retinopathy cases. Serum magnesium level was 1.86 ± 0.26 in NDPR (Non proliferative diabetic retinopathy). Serum magnesium level was 1.64 ± 0.25 in PDR (Proliferative diabetic retinopathy). So it is highly suggestive of hypomagnesemia to occur at an increased risk diabetic retinopathy among patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. Magnesium deficiency was associated with increased risk of diabetic retinopathy and poor glycemic control. Dietary supplementation may be advised to prevent such complications and improve glycemic control.

KEY WORDS: glycemic control, magnesium, retinopathy, type 2 diabetes mellitus

INTRODUCTION:

India has the largest number of diabetic patients in the world. It is increasing particularly in the most developing countries severely. Diabetes mellitus (DM) refers to a group of common metabolic disorders that share the phenotype of hyperglycaemia. Depending upon the etiology of the DM, factors contributing to hyperglycaemia include reduced insulin secretion, decreased glucose utilization, and increased glucose production. The metabolic dysregulation associated with DM causes secondary pathophysiologic changes in multiple organ systems, leading to microvascular (retinopathy, nephropathy, neuropathy) and macrovascular (coronary heart disease, peripheral arterial disease, cerebrovascular disease)^[1]. Diabetes mellitus is a group of metabolic diseases characterized by hyperglycemia resulting

from defects in insulin secretion, insulin action, or both. The chronic hyperglycemia of diabetes is associated with long-term damage, dysfunction, and failure of various organs, especially the eyes, kidneys, nerves, heart, and blood vessels^[2].

Magnesium (Mg⁺²) is one of the important components of many foods such as grains, nuts and green leafy vegetables, and it plays a key role in many fundamental biological processes, including energy metabolism. (Mg⁺²) has received considerable attention for its potential role in improving insulin sensitivity and preventing diabetes and its cardiovascular complications^[3].

It is claimed that (Mg⁺²) deficiency is common in diabetic patients and there is an inverse relationship between (Mg⁺²) intake and incidence of Type2 Diabetes mellitus T2DM. The magnesium is an essential cofactor of more than 300 enzymes including those important in glycolysis, neuromuscular transmission, synthesis of carbohydrates, proteins, lipid and nucleic acids, and it has a role in insulin's secretion, its binding and its activity. Experimental researches have shown that patients with diabetic retinopathy present low concentration of plasma magnesium, disposing to a higher risk of advanced

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retinopathy^[4].

In patients with diabetic retinopathy, lower level of magnesium predicting a greater risk for diabetic retinopathy. Diabetic retinopathy is one of the leading causes of blindness in the world in the base of India.¹⁰ Using new surgical and medical techniques, the incidence of blindness can be reduced up to 95%. Decrease in visual acuity in diabetic retinopathy is either associated with maculopathy or proliferative complications of it. Hypomagnesemia has been reported to occur at an increased frequency among patients with type 2 diabetes compared with their counterparts without diabetes. Hypomagnesemia has been linked to poor glycemic control. Although, it is generally believed that stringent metabolic control delays the development of late complications in diabetes mellitus, it has not been demonstrated conclusively that such control holds back the development of diabetic retinopathy. Many studies have been undergone to find out the precipitated factors of retinopathy such as duration and type of diabetes, hyperglycemia, hypomagnesemia and increased urinary total protein levels. Hypomagnesemia has been demonstrated in patients with diabetic retinopathy, lower levels of magnesium predicting a greater risk for diabetic retinopathy.^[5,6,7]

Diabetic retinopathy is one of the commonest causes of blindness in adults in the age group 30 to 65 years in developed countries. During the 1st two decades of disease, nearly all patients with T1DM and >60% with T2DM have retinopathy.^[8] Twenty one percent of T2DM patients have presented with retinopathy at first visit. There are some classification as given below:

A. Nonproliferative Diabetic Retinopathy (NPDR): Mild type: Presence of 1 micro aneurysm with one or more of the following : a) Retinal haemorrhage; b) Hard and soft exudates. 2. Moderate type: a) Presence of Haemorrhage/ micro aneurysms or; b) Presence of both in at least one quadrant with one or more of the following: Soft exudates; venous beading and intra retinal microvascular abnormalities. 3. Severe type: a) Haemorrhage or micro aneurysms or; b) Both in all quadrants; c) Venous beading in two or more quadrants; d) intra retinal microvascular abnormalities in at least one quadrant. B. Proliferative Diabetic Retinopathy (PDR): 1. Early: One or more of the following: a) NVE; b) NVD; c) Vitreous or preretinal haemorrhage; d) NVE < ½ disc area. 2. High risk: One or more of the following:

a) NVD > ¼ - 1/3 disc area; b) NVD with vitreous or preretinal haemorrhage; c) NVE > ½ disc area. Preretinal or vitreous haemorrhage. 3. Advanced PDR: a) High risk PDR, traction retinal detachment involving macula or b) Vitreous haemorrhage obscuring ability to grade NVD or NVE and IRMA – Intraretinal micro vascular abnormalities. NVE – Neovascularisation elsewhere. NVD – Neovascularisation over the disc. Clinical features of Retinopathy: Micro aneurysms; Retinal haemorrhage; Exudates; Cotton wool spots; Neovascularisation of retina and iris; Subhyaloid haemorrhage and Vitreous haemorrhage and fibrosis. Macular edema can occur at any stage of diabetic retinopathy. Non proliferative diabetic retinopathy usually appears at end of first decade or early second decade in cases of type 2 diabetes mellitus. Proliferative diabetic retinopathy usually appears within 5 years of non-proliferative diabetic retinopathy. Pregnancy, uncontrolled diabetes mellitus, uncontrolled HT can accelerate these changes. Other ocular complications: Cataract; Glaucoma; Retinal detachment; Macular edema Investigations for retinopathy: Visual acuity; Fundus examination; Fundus fluorescein angiography; Slit lamp examination. Treatment options for retinopathy: Laser photocoagulation; Injection of steroids. Anti-vascular endothelial growth factor.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

One hundred patients with type 2 DM with retinopathy admitted in People's College of Medical Sciences and Research Centre hospital between May 2019 to April 2020. Sample size was 100 diagnosed cases of type 2 DM which are further correlated for comparison of magnesium levels, with retinopathy. Method of collection of data: Patients with type 2 DM admitted to PCMS & RC underwent the following tests; FBS (fasting blood sugar); PPBS (post prandial; measured two hours after a standard meal); Fasting serum magnesium levels; Fundoscopy and Diabetics were divided into controlled (HbA1C <7), uncontrolled (HbA1C >7). Study variables included fasting serum Magnesium levels, HbA1c. Inclusion criteria: All cases of type 2 DM and age/sex matched on diabetic patients admitted to PCMS hospital in age between 20-70 years were included.

Exclusion criteria:

(a) Patient below 20 and above 70yrs; (b) Patient

with COPD; (c) Patient on diuretics and receiving magnesium supplements; (d) Patient with history of alcohol abuse; (e) Pregnant women; (f) Patient with anaemia (according to WHO guideline $\leq 11\text{g/dl}$ both in males and females) and Patient with history of epilepsy.

Sample collection: After overnight fasting for 8 – 12 hrs, approx. 3ml blood sample for serum magnesium red top plane tube, 2ml for HbA1c in EDTA vial. Samples was centrifuged at 3000rpm for 10 min. Serum was separated and used for analysis. **Estimation of serum magnesium:** By spectrophotometric method using xylidyl blue dye. Estimation of serum magnesium : By spectrophotometric method using xylidyl blue dye. **PRINCIPLE:** Colorimetric endpoint method. In alkaline solution, magnesium forms a purple complex with xylidyl blue, diazonium salt.

The magnesium concentration was measured photometrically via the decrease in the xylidyl blue absorbance. Kit contents: R1 - TRIS/6-aminocaproic acid buffer: 500 mmol/L, pH 11.25; EGTA: 129 $\mu\text{mol/L}$; preservative; R2 - Xylidyl blue: 0.28 mmol/L; detergent; Preservative Diluent NaCl 9%, 50 mL; Specimen: Fresh unhemolysed serum was taken, as a hemolysed sample may falsely elevate magnesium levels; Glycohemoglobin Test: Boronate Affinity Chromatography.

The product name and generic name Glycohemoglobin Test Kit Package Insert Updated : 2nd , January, 2019. Materials Provided and main Components. XPRESS A1C Glycohemoglobin Test Strip is packed in a plastic vial. XPRESS A1C Glycohemoglobin Test Kit comes in the following package: Vial package (25 Tests/Vial, 1 Vial/Kit); 1 Code Chip \times 1 piece; HbA1c Test strip \times 25 pieces; Sampler \times 25 pieces; Buffer A \times 1 bottle; Buffer B \times 1 bottle. Data collection procedure: Data was collected after assaying blood sample of subjects. Statistical analysis: Student T test has been used to find the significance of mean pattern of serum magnesium between cases and controls by SPSS software. p-value ≤ 0.05 is considered as significant.

RESULTS:

The study was conducted in PCMS Bhopal on 100 DM type 2 with complication 30 DM type 2 without complication patients, taking into consideration all the inclusion & exclusion criteria

for comparison of serum magnesium levels and complications of diabetes. The mean serum magnesium levels were $1.89 \pm 0.18\text{ mg/dl}$ and $2.23 \pm 0.28\text{ mg/dl}$ in cases (DM type 2 with complication) and controls (DM type 2 without complication) respectively. The mean serum magnesium levels in patients with NDPR and PDR were 1.86 ± 0.26 and 1.64 ± 0.25 respectively.

In our study serum Mg+2 was found to be significantly decreased in diabetic patients type 2 with retinopathy. Hypomagnesemia has been reported in patients with diabetic retinopathy. The present study revealed a definite association between diabetic retinopathy and low serum magnesium levels. Patients with diabetic retinopathy and those without it had a mean serum magnesium level of 1.86 mg/dl (NPDR), 1.64 (PDR) and 2.03 mg/dl (NO RETINOPATHY) respectively.

Table 1 : Comparison of serum Magnesium Level between Groups.

Serum Magnesium (Normal =1.8-2.5 mg/dl)	Mean \pm SD	t-value	p-value
Cases	1.89 ± 0.18	5.38	0.001
Controls	2.23 ± 0.28		

Table 2 : Percentage of cases with diabetic retinopathy.

Complications	Cases(n=100)	Controls(n=30)
Retinopathy	47(47%)	0 (0%)

DISCUSSION:

In our study serum Mg+2 was found to be significantly decreased in diabetic patients type 2 with retinopathy. Hypomagnesemia has been reported in patients with diabetic retinopathy. With lower serum magnesium levels predicting a greater risk of severe diabetic retinopathy^[9].

The present study revealed a definite association between diabetic retinopathy and low serum magnesium levels. The observations are similar to our reports. So, probably hypomagnesemia

Graph 1 :Comparison of Serum Magnesium values.

Graph 2: Percentage of patients with complication.

Table 3 :Comparison of serum Magnesium level in patients with and without retinopathy in uncontrolled Diabetic patients.

Type of retinopathy	Serum Magnesium	f-value	p-value
No Retinopathy (n=53)	2.03 ± 0.33		
NPDR (n=29)	1.86 ± 0.26	9.72	0.01*
PDR (n=18)	1.64 ± 0.25		

NPDR- Non proliferative diabetic retinopathy PDR- Proliferative diabetic retinopathy.

Graph 3 :Comparison of serum Magnesium level in patients with and without retinopathy in uncontrolled Diabetic patients.

and increased serum cholesterol and triglyceride levels are responsible for microvascular changes in diabetes leading to retinopathy.^[10]

Hypomagnesemia has been reported in patients with diabetic retinopathy. With lower serum magnesium levels predicting a greater risk of severe diabetic retinopathy. The present study revealed a definite association between diabetic retinopathy and low serum magnesium levels. Patients with diabetic retinopathy and those without it had a mean serum magnesium level of 1.86 mg/dl (NPDR), 1.64 (PDR) and 2.03 mg/dl (NO RETINOPATHY) respectively. These observations are similar to other reports. Grifton et al. have proposed the inositol transport theory to explain this association^[11,12].

CONCLUSION:

Serum Mg²⁺ estimation is very important & plays significant role in prognostic evaluation of diabetes and prevent complications. Serum magnesium levels were significant low in DM type 2 with complication when compared to DM type 2 without complication. Levels of serum magnesium were low in uncontrolled type 2 diabetics than those in whom diabetes was controlled. Serum magnesium was found to be a factor associated with diabetic retinopathy. Serum magnesium is a factor in type 2 diabetes and associated with various complications. Hence it is worth measuring serum magnesium levels in patients with type DM and probably correlate their

relationship with various complications.

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Cite this article as: Rajpoot LS, Dharwadkar KR, Chandrakar S, Jain A, Sharma A. Association of Serum Magnesium Level with Retinopathy in Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus. *PJSR.* 2021;14(1):18-23.
Source of Support : Nil, Conflict of Interest: None declared.